

Synthesis of Some Unsymmetrical Thioureas and 3-Aryl-2-Aryl Imino-4-Thiazolidinones: Part II

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Twelve new unsymmetrical thioureas derived from *p*-amino-*n*-butyl and isobutyl benzoates and twelve 3-aryl-2-arylimino-4-thiazolidinones have been synthesised with a view to studying their biological activity.

Due to the interesting bactericidal and anti-tubercular¹ activity of aryl thioureas, some unsymmetrical thioureas have been synthesised from the reaction of *p*-amino-*n*-butyl and isobutyl benzoates with different aryl isothiocyanates. Marked antiparasitic and hypoglycemic properties are also exhibited by some substituted thioureas² and halogenated thioureas³. The therapeutic importance of 4-thiazolidinones and their mercurated derivatives as anti-tubercular⁴ and antifungal⁵⁻⁶ agents encouraged us to synthesise some new 4-thiazolidinones in the series, as strong fungicides. Horsfall and Rich⁷ have suggested that carbonyl group incorporated in a nitrogen heterocyclic imparts fungitoxicity in the molecule.

Keeping these facts in view 3-aryl-2-arylimino-4-thiazolidinones were prepared⁸⁻⁹ by condensation of unsymmetrical thioureas with chloroacetic acid.

EXPERIMENTAL

1-(p-Iodophenyl)-3-(p-n-butyl benzoate thiourea : *p*-Amino *n*-butyl benzoate (1.5 gm, .008 mole) and *p*-iodophenyl isothiocyanate (2.1 g, .008 mole) were dissolved in alcohol separately and mixed. The resulting mixture was refluxed for an hour and cooled. The crystalline solid thus obtained was filtered and washed with ether. Crystallisation with ethanol afforded pure sample, m.p. 160°; yield 70%. Found : N, 6.3; C₁₈H₁₉IN₂O₂S requires; N, 6.16%.

Other unsymmetrical thioureas were prepared similarly from *p*-amino-*n*-butyl and isobutyl benzoates with different isothiocyanates. With *o*-tolyl and *m*-tolyl isothiocyanates, thioureas were not obtained in crystalline state after refluxing for an hour but on standing for two to three days crystalline products were obtained. In spite of maintaining different reaction conditions 1-(*m*-)tolyl 3-(*p*-) *n*-butyl benzoate thiourea was always obtained in gummy state. The analytical data and m.p. are recorded in Table I.

3-(α-Pyridyl)-2-(o-tolyl)imino-4-thiazolidinone : 1-(α-)Pyridyl-3-(o-) tolyl thiourea (2.9 gm, .012 mole) (prepared¹⁰ from 2-aminopyridine and *o*-tolylisothiocyanate) and monochloroacetic acid (1.5 gm, .012 mole) were refluxed with fused sodium acetate (1.3 gm, .015

TABLE I

1-Aryl-3-(p-) butyl benzoate thioureas

Sl. No.	Nature of R	Nature of R'	M.P. °C	Yield %	Molecular Formula	% N	
						Found	Calc.
1.	<i>n</i> -Butyl	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	130	70	C ₁₉ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	7.8	8.18
2.	-do-	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	Gummy	—	-do-	—	8.18
3.	-do-	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	110	72	-do-	8.3	8.18
4.	-do-	<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	130	78	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ BrN ₂ O ₂ S	6.5	6.88
5.	-do-	<i>p</i> -Phenetyl	145	75	C ₂₀ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₃ S	7.8	7.53
6.	<i>iso</i> -Butyl	-do-	130	70	-do-	7.3	7.53
7.	-do-	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	115	71	C ₁₉ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	7.9	8.18
8.	-do-	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	110	73	-do-	8.4	8.18
9.	-do-	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	145	76	-do-	8.3	8.18
10.	-do-	<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	155	79	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ BrN ₂ O ₂ S	6.6	6.88
11.	-do-	<i>p</i> -Iodophenyl	180	68	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ IN ₂ O ₂ S	6.3	6.16

TABLE II

3-Aryl-2-arylimino-4-thiazolidinones*

Sl. No.	Nature of R	Nature of R'	Yield %	M.P. °C	Molecular Formula	% N	
						Found	Calc.
1.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	<i>p</i> Bromophenyl	60	165	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ BrN ₂ OS	7.9	7.75
2.	-do-	<i>p</i> -Phenetyl	65	130	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	7.6	7.72
3.	-do-	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	67	155	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	8.3	8.03
4.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	phenyl <i>p</i> -(<i>n</i> -)butylcarboxylate	48	150	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ ClN ₂ O ₃ S	6.4	6.68
5.	-do-	Phenyl <i>p</i> -(<i>iso</i> -)butylcarboxylate	50	145	-do-	6.9	6.68
6.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	-do-	45	170	-do-	6.6	6.68
7.	<i>p</i> -Phenetyl	-do-	60	175	C ₂₂ H ₂₅ ClN ₂ O ₄ S	6.4	6.24
8.	-do-	Phenyl <i>p</i> -(<i>n</i> -)butylcarboxylate	55	190	-do-	5.9	6.24
9.	<i>p</i> -Iodophenyl	-do-	53	120	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ ClIN ₂ O ₃ S	5.5	5.27
10.	-do-	Phenyl <i>p</i> -(<i>iso</i> -)butylcarboxylate	gummy	—	-do-	—	5.27
11.	<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	-do-	gummy	—	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ ClBrN ₂ O ₃ S	—	5.90
12.	-do-	Phenyl <i>p</i> -(<i>n</i> -)butylcarboxylate	50	150	-do-	5.7	5.90

* The free bases except No. 1 were gummy. The elemental analysis and melting point recorded in Table II are of their hydrochlorides.

mole) in presence of ethanol (10 ml) for 4-5 hrs. The resulting mixture was poured into ice cold water. A precipitate was obtained which was filtered and washed several times with hot water, yield (1.9 gm) 60%. Crystallisation of the product with ethanol gave a sample m.p. 140°. Found : N, 14.5; $C_{15}H_{13}N_3OS$ requires, N, 14.8%.

Other unsymmetrical thiazolidinones were prepared similarly and analyses and m.p. are recorded in Table II.

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